

TO THE LANGUAGES OF THE FINNO-UGRIC PEOPLE
THE INFLUENCE OF THE KHORAZIM LANGUAGE

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Аннотация: Мақолада қадим замонлардан Хоразм воҳасининг Жанубий Сибирь халқлари билан иқтисодий ва маданий алоқалари тарихига бағишланган бўлиб, шу иқтисодий алоқалар таъсирида Сибирнинг фин-угор халқлари тиллари ривожланишида хоразмий тилининг ўрни хусусида сўз юритилган.

Калит сўзлар: А.И.Наймарк, В.В.Понарядов, С.Л.Волин, В.А.Лившиц, Жанубий Сибирь, финн-угор халқлари, хоразмий тили, хоразмий ёзуви, Волгабўйи, Жанубий Урал, Коми – Пермь.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена истории экономических и культурных связей Хорезмского оазиса с народами Южной Сибири с древнейших времен, а также роли хорезмийского языка в развитии языков финно-угорских народов Сибири под влиянием этих экономических отношений.

Ключевые слова: А.И. Наймарк, В.В. Понарядов, С.Л. Волин, В.А. Лившиц, Южная Сибирь, финно-угорские народы, хорезмийский язык, хорезмийская письменность, Поволжье, Южный Урал, Коми - Пермь.

Annotation: The article is devoted to the history of economic and cultural ties between the Khorezm oasis and the peoples of Southern Siberia since ancient times, as well as the role of the Khorezm language in the development of the languages of the Finno-Ugric peoples of Siberia under the influence of these economic relations.

Keywords: A.I. Naimark, V.V. Ponaryadov, S.L. Volin, V.A. Livshits, Southern Siberia, Finno-Ugric peoples, Khorezm language, Khorezm script, Volga region, Southern Urals, Komi-Perm.

The Khorezm people, who have been living in the lower basin of the Amudarya since ancient times, once had their own native language and script. The Khorezmian script was created on the basis of the Aramaic alphabet, while the Khorezmian language belonged to the Eastern Iranian dialect of the Iranian language group. Khorezm writing gradually lost its ancient appearance under the influence of the Arabic alphabet starting from the 8th century. The ancient Khorezm language joined the group of dead languages by the 14th century AD.

In general, scholars express different opinions on the issue of ancient Khorezm writing. For example, one group of scientists says that the Khorezm script was formed at the same time as the ancient state of Khorezm in the 8th-7th centuries BC, while another group of scientists says that it belongs to the 5th-4th centuries BC based on the oldest writing sample found in the territory of Khorezm, i.e., present-day Oybogirkala (Ellikkala district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan) located found in the monument and the inscription of these centuries for the time being It is considered the oldest example of writing in Central Asia [Livshits V.A., Mambetullaev M.M.: 42; Mambetullaev M.M., 1990:128].

The period of formation and development of the Khorezm script includes approximately the following stages: 1. BC. VIII-IV centuries. 2. BC IV - III centuries AD. 3. III-VIII centuries. 4. VIII-XI centuries.

The ancient Khorezm script was based on the Aramaic script, only 20 letters were used instead of the 22 in the Aramaic script.

Information about ancient Khorezm writing was given by medieval scholars Abu Raykhan Beruni and 13th century jurist Najmiddin al-Hazini.

In the course of archaeological research, examples of ancient Khorezm writing were found and studied in Tuproqkala, Koykirilgankala, Khumbuztepa, Mizdakhkan, Oyboghirkala monuments of Khorezm.

Scientists such as A.A. Freyman, I.M. Oransky, Z. Hertzfeld, S.L. Volin, V. Livshits, M. Ishakov made a great contribution to the study of Khorezm language and writing.

Khorezm's language and writing has been slightly changed under the influence of the language and writing of neighboring countries and invaders from far and near, and has gone through stages of crisis and growth. Especially the Arab invasion gave him a fatal blow. However, the studies conducted on the study of the Khorezm language influenced the development of the languages of other nations for various reasons. This is especially evident in the languages of the peoples who lived in the regions north of Khorezm. After all, Khorezm has long been connected not with the regions to the south, south-west or east of itself, but with the northern regions, to be more precise, the Volga, South Urals, Kama river banks (including the republics of Bashkortostan, Tatarstan, Udmurtia, Perm, Komi-Perm of the Russian Federation). the region's relations with the tribes of the region, or rather trade relations, were relatively well developed. These water relations have existed for a very long time, and their roots go back to the III millennium BC, and it should be emphasized once again that trade-trade relations are of primary importance and determined the characteristics of these relations [Naimark A. I.: 31].

Starting from the end of the 6th century BC, these relations become stronger. Khorezm served as a unique bridge connecting the settled agricultural southern civilization with the northern civilizations of nomadic pastoralists [Tairov A.D.: 54; Yagodin V. N.: 192].

Therefore, the linguistic studies conducted in these regions show the existence of words directly derived from the Khorezm language in the languages of the peoples living in these regions since ancient times.

As a result of linguistic research, it has been proven that some words in the languages of Komi - Udmurts, Bashkirs and Ossetians living in the Perm region belong to the Khorezm language. For example, the word "zarńi" (gold) in the Komi-Udmurt language is derived from the word "zrny(zarnī - gold)" in the ancient Khorezm language (in other languages belonging to the ancient eastern Iranian group, for example, Sogdian (zyrn(zi/ern)) and Middle- Khorezmi word is much closer than words denoting gold in Iranian (Zarr) languages) [Ponaryadov V. V.: 693].

The words "eziś" in Komi and "azveś" in Udmurt mean silver metal or silver coin, just like "ævzīst// ævzestæ" in Ossetian and "ažīd" or "azīž" in Old Khorezm. As we mentioned above, many researchers have proved that the ancient Khorezm language had a strong influence on the Ossetian language [Abaev V. I.].

Similarly, the word "ńebęg" in the Komi language is understood in the sense of a book, like "nbyk-nibęk" in the ancient Khorezm language [Ponaryadov V. V.: 695]. There are many such terms. However, many researchers point out that due to the insufficient study of Khorezm language and writing, it is not possible to fully study this issue. If we take into account the ancient existence of Finno-Ugric tribes in the region of the Volga, Southern Urals, along the banks of the Kama River (the territories of the present-day Russian Federation of Bashkortostan, Tatarstan, Udmurtia, Perm, Komi-Perm lands), then the current Finnish language is also historically and linguistically It would be an important thing for us to study.

For this reason, first of all, in cooperation with Finnish and Russian antiquarians and literary scholars, the researches on the language and writing of the ancient Finns, the ancient Siberian Finno-Ugric peoples and the ancient Khorezm, their unique monuments, as well as the wider study of the trade relations between these regions and Khorezm were launched. it is necessary to put and conduct a lot of research in this field, which in the future will be important in fully revealing the most problematic pages of the history of ancient Russia, Finland and Khorezm.

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